

Wearable System for Inclusive Cultural Tourism based on Artificial Intelligence

Dimitris K. Iakovidis¹, Evaggelos Spyrou^{2,3}, and Artur Krukowski⁴

¹Dept. of Computer Science and Biomedical Informatics, University of Thessaly, Greece

²Institute of Informatics & Telecommunications, NCSR – “Demokritos”, Greece

³Dept. of Computer Science & Telecommunications, University of Thessaly, Greece

⁴Intracom S. A. Telecom Solutions, Greece

Cultural tourism is a right for everyone, including people with disabilities. In this work we present a novel wearable system aiming to enhance the user experiences of individuals visiting outdoor cultural environments, such as the Historic Triangle of Athens. The developed system is based on Artificial Intelligence to offer enhanced touristic experiences to modern travellers, especially to people with visual and kinetic disabilities. The proposed solution is a digital system in the form of wearable smart-glasses, equipped with a stereoscopic camera, and two main software modules: a) An intelligent module, that incorporates machine learning algorithms, and enables the interpretation of the video scenes captured by the camera into audible information for the users. This way, the system can automatically recognize sites of interest, such as monuments, and describe them to the user. It can also automatically create video summaries of the sites they visit. The system provides additional functionalities for people with visual impairments, such as automatic detection of obstacles, and audio-based navigation, enabling them to avoid obstacles and safely navigate in outdoor cultural environments. b) A cloud connection module provides audiovisual streaming services through the internet enabling real-time interaction between the physically touring users and remote users, e.g., friends. This way, the travellers may share their experiences and enable remote users to virtually tour at the same places. Such a feature is important especially for users with kinetic disabilities that are not capable of travelling, and for blind users, who can use it to receive assistance from remote users, in difficult situations where the automatic navigation may

prove to be insufficient. The results of the evaluation of the different modules of the system validate their effectiveness for the described functionalities. User evaluation studies are being performed, with initial results indicating its capacity as an assistive system for visually impaired individuals. The presented system is expected to have a considerable socioeconomic impact as its applicability extends to other tourism domains beyond cultural tourism. This research has been co-financed by the European Union and Greek national funds through the Operational Program Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship and Innovation, under the call Research-Creat-Innovate (project code:T1EDK-02070).